

Welcome to HERITALISE Newsletter!

HERITALISE brings together communities, researchers, and institutions to rethink the role of heritage in today's digital challenges. Through collaborative research, pilots, and cross-sector dialogue, we aim to co-create new pathways that bridge the past with the future, making heritage more relevant, accessible, and impactful.

Thank you for walking this path with us, and for continuing the mission ahead!

- Full name: Heritage buildings and objects' digitisation & visualisation within the cloud
- Acronym: HERITALISE
- Number of partners: 17
- Start date: 1st January 2025
- Duration: 48 months
- EC funding: 4 196 368,71 €

Partners acronyms: IDP, University St. Andrews, Tekniker, Centro Conservazione Restauro La Venaria Reale, Fundación Santa María La Real, Politecnico di Torino, Comet Global Innovation, BDTA, Cyprus University of Technology, Open Geospatial Consortium, West Highland Museum, Timespan, Europeaana, Heritage Malta, European Museum Academy, EIM

NEWS

An Introduction to the West Highland Museum Demonstration Site

WEST HIGHLAND MUSEUM

West Highland Museum is one of the four demonstration centres for the Heritalise project. Situated in Fort William, Scotland, it was founded in 1922 and is one of the oldest museums in the Scottish Highlands.

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Villa Portelli: Where Memory Lives in Layers

The pilot in Malta, Villa Portelli, aims to create a Memory Twin: a digital model that does not simply replicate walls and windows, but revives the emotions, narratives and uses the historical values of the building, turning it into a national monument.

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HERITALISE Project Starts

The HERITALISE project held its Kick-off on the 24th in Barcelona. HERITALISE is about digitisation, tool development and the use of AI to help with the data processing aspects of the workflow. Collections from demonstration sites located in Scotland, Italy and Malta will be used as use cases, and the results will be a valuable contribution to the Cultural Heritage Cloud.

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SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

3D Research Challenges in Cultural Heritage V [▶ DOWNLOAD](#)

3D Research Challenges in Cultural Heritage IV [▶ DOWNLOAD](#)

European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH)

The Cultural Heritage Cloud or European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) is a European Union initiative to create a shared digital infrastructure that connects cultural heritage institutions and professionals across the EU. It will provide specific digital collaboration tools for the sector while removing barriers for smaller and more remote institutions.

The Cultural Heritage Cloud aims to add a digital dimension to cultural heritage preservation, conservation, restoration, and enhancement by providing cutting-edge technology for artefact digitisation and artwork research.

This platform is developed by ECHOES (European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science), a project funded by the European Commission and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).

Visit the [ECHOES](#) for more information!

EVENTS

DIGITAL HERITAGE 2025

The Heritage Cloud Summit will be held in the heart of the historic city of Siena, Italy.

8-12 September 2025, Siena (Italy)

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Digital Heritage 2025 Congress

In September, partners POLITO, TEK, and USTAN will be present in Siena at the Digital Heritage 2025 Congress to present a paper on the work to date in Heritalise.

CIPA 2025 SEOUL

Heritage Conservation from Bits
From Digital Documentation to Data-driven Heritage Conservation

25 - 29 August 2025

"Heritage Conservation from Bits: From Digital Documentation to Data-driven Heritage Conservation" at CIPA 2025

The partners TEKNIKER and Polito will attend the CIPA Congress 2025 in Seoul, presenting on Heritalise. We are looking forward to this event!

WORKSHOP #8: Opportunities and Tools from the Cultural Heritage Cloud (ECCCH-ECHOES) for Digital Archaeology

OPPORTUNITIES AND TOOLS FROM THE CULTURAL HERITAGE CLOUD FOR DIGITAL ARCHAEOLOGY

MONDAY MAY 5TH, 2025
from 09.00 to 18.00 EET

WORKSHOP #8: Opportunities and Tools from the Cultural Heritage Cloud (ECCCH-ECHOES) for Digital Archaeology

The partners USTAN, POLITO, TEKNIKER, CUT & HM, attended the workshop organised by ECHOES, where they presented Heritalise and were able to establish relationships with the sister projects Textailles and AUTOMATA.

Webinar 'How can CEN/TC 442 support digitalization of data in design and product standards?'

Wednesday 2025-05-12
Online
10:00 - 11:00 CET
Pavina KARBAGIANNI

CEN442 PLENARY WEBINAR

A BDTA partner attended a webinar by CENELEC, one of the leading European standardisation bodies, last March. This event is fundamental for Heritalise, as it presented a roadmap for future DTW standardisation initiatives—one of them focused on photogrammetry in Heritage.

SPES National Committee 8 (Photogrammetry) Online Talk

The Potential of AI for 3D Scene Digitization - Recent Learning-based Innovations on Handling Challenging Scenarios

Abstract of the talk

The Potential of AI for 3D Scene Digitization. Recent Learning-based Innovations on Handling Challenging Scenarios. Talk by Prof. Michael Weinmann

Partner Polito attended this Talk to learn about the state of the art of AI in 3D scanning.

HERITALISE YOUTUBE CHANNEL

Don't miss the videos we are uploading to our YouTube channel.

Villa Portelli - Malta

PILOT

[▶ WATCH THE VIDEO](#)

In this Newsletter, we present to you the Malta Pilot images: Villa Portelli.

Don't miss the videos, subscribe to our YouTube channel!

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Be the first to learn about project events and activities!

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<https://heritalise-ecch.eu/>

